

Dissociation Constants of CdSO_4 and $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ at a Number of Temperatures and the Related Thermodynamic Functions

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Values of the dissociation constants of CdSO_4 and $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ and the corresponding thermodynamic functions in aqueous solution have been determined over the temperature range 293.15–308.15 K in steps of 5 K from e.m.f. measurements with cell,

pK values for CdSO_4 at 293.15, 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K are 2.84, 3.00, 3.30 and 3.41, and the values of ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° at 298.15 K are 1.1 kJ mol⁻¹, -64.3 kJ mol⁻¹ and -273.2 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Beyond an ionic strength of 0.02 mol dm⁻³, CdSO_4 reacts with SO_4^{2-} forming $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$. Values of the logarithm of association constant K_a of $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ at these temperatures are 0.18, 0.29, 0.48 and 0.66. The values of ΔG_a° , ΔH_a° and ΔS_a° corresponding to association at 298.15 K are -1.66 kJ mol⁻¹, 53.60 kJ mol⁻¹ and 185.3 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

ASSUMING that CdSO_4 in aqueous solution dissociates as $\text{CdSO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$, Davies² first determined the dissociation constant (K) of CdSO_4 conductometrically at 291.15 K. He re-determined³ K at the same temperature conductometrically using his equation for activity coefficient. McBain and van Rysselberg³ found that in mixtures of CdSO_4 and MgSO_4 , $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ is also formed. Jena and Prasad⁴ determined the values of dissociation constants of CdSO_4 as well as $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ at 308.15 K only (on the basis of certain assumptions) from e.m.f. measurements of a number of cells, some of which contained salt-bridge. The assumptions are perhaps not completely true, Cd^{2+} is known to be hydrolysed in aqueous solution and the value of K has been found at 308.15 K only. The thermodynamics of dissociation of either CdSO_4 or $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ in aqueous solution is not yet known. So cell (C-1) was set up to determine the dissociation constants of both CdSO_4 and $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ at a number of temperatures.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of G R. grade. Hg_2SO_4 was prepared electrolytically⁵. CdSO_4 and H_2SO_4 were taken in mole ratio of 5 : 1 and the minimum concentration of H_2SO_4 in solution was 8×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ so as to prevent Hg_2SO_4 from being hydrolysed⁶. Experimental solutions having ionic

strength less than 0.05 mol dm⁻³ were prepared in double-distilled water strictly at the temperature of the experiment, and were deoxygenated by passing pure and pre-saturated N_2 for 10–12 h before putting them in cell. The cells were set up at four temperatures, viz 293.15, 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K. The details of setting up of cells, thermostat, potentiometer assembly etc. were similar to those described earlier⁷. The e.m.f. of the duplicate cells set-up agreed with one another within ± 0.01 mV. The mean of the two e.m.f. values were recorded and the related data at 298.15 K are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) is given by equation (1),

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{k}{2} \log [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] - \frac{k}{2} (\log f_{\text{H}^+}^2 + f_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}) \quad (1)$$

where, $k = 2.3026 RT/F$ and

$$E^\circ = E_{\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{SO}_4^{2-}}^\circ - E_{\text{Pt}/\text{Q, QH}_2}^\circ$$

It was found⁸ earlier that equation (2) fairly correctly represents the activity coefficient of an ion in dilute solution,

$$-\log f_i = AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu} - b_i \mu \quad (2)$$

where, A is Debye-Hückel constant (mol^{-1/2} dm^{3/2}) and b is an empirical constant which is additive and reasonably independent of the composition of ionic

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC MOLARITIES AND MOLARITIES OF VARIOUS IONIC SPECIES IN CELL (C-1)

Temp. = 298.15 K									
c_2	c_1	E abs. V	$[\text{H}^+]$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$	$[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$	$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$	μ	K_c $\times 10^8$	$\log K_c - 8A\sqrt{\mu}$
0.004 01	0.000 81	0.165 36	0.001 33	0.003 63	0.000 54	0.002 57	0.014 27	8.801 04	8.457
0.004 22	0.000 86	0.163 27	0.001 39	0.004 03	0.000 50	0.003 00	0.015 92	11.737 86	8.555
0.004 64	0.000 94	0.160 71	0.001 50	0.004 31	0.000 48	0.003 27	0.017 06	13.551 63	8.599
0.005 27	0.001 07	0.155 89	0.001 68	0.004 77	0.000 45	0.003 71	0.018 93	16.695 00	8.662
0.005 70	0.001 15	0.154 96	0.001 80	0.004 85	0.000 44	0.003 76	0.019 25	16.730 28	8.658
0.006 33	0.001 28	0.151 55	0.001 94	0.005 75	0.000 40	0.004 69	0.022 96	25.441 04	8.788
0.006 75	0.001 37	0.149 68	0.002 06	0.005 97	0.000 39	0.004 89	0.023 87	27.030 83	8.802
0.007 38	0.001 50	0.147 25	0.002 24	0.006 16	0.000 38	0.005 04	0.024 66	27.720 00	8.803
0.009 49	0.001 93	0.140 32	0.002 78	0.007 23	0.000 34	0.006 04	0.029 15	36.696 64	8.869

All concentrations and ionic strengths are in mol dm^{-3} .

atmosphere in dilute solutions provided the composition of the ionic atmosphere is not drastically changed. Putting equation (2) in equation (1),

$$E = E^0 - \frac{k}{2} \log [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 3k. A\sqrt{\mu} - kb\mu \quad (3)$$

where, $b = 2b_{\text{H}^+} + b_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$. Values of E^0 and b were given by Sharma and Prasad⁹ at 298.15 and 308.15 K, while the values at 293.15 and 303.15 K were obtained by us from studies of cell (C-2) in conjunction with the literature value¹⁰ of $E_{\text{Pb}^{2+}/\text{Pb}, \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}^0$,

K_A , defined as $[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}] / [\text{HSO}_4^-]$ is related to the dissociation constant K_2 of HSO_4^- by equation (4),

$$\log K_A - 4A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K_2 - b_1\mu \quad (4)$$

where b_1 is an empirical constant whose values at 293.15 and 308.15 K were given by Sharma and Prasad⁹, and values at 293.15 and 303.15 K were found by us. Values of solubility product K_{sp} of Hg_2SO_4 and b_2 which are given by equation (5) were found by Sharma and Prasad¹¹ at 298.15 and 308.15 K and by us at 293.15 and 303.15 K.

$$\log [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}] = \log K_{sp} + 8A\sqrt{\mu} - b_2\mu \quad (5)$$

If we assume that H_2SO_4 , Hg_2SO_4 and CdSO_4 found in cell solution of cell (C-1) dissociate according to the scheme,

Then,

$$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}} = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4} + [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4} + [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{CdSO}_4} \quad (6)$$

and the ionic strength of the solution,

$$\mu = c_1 + 4[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] - 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4} \quad (7)$$

since, $[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4}$. All the ionic species in solution are hydrated and charged but the hydration has not been shown for the sake of convenience. Now by a process similar to that described earlier⁷ we find out the concentration of various ionic species correct to 10 micro mol dm^{-3} .

Denoting $[\text{Cd}^{2+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]/[\text{CdSO}_4]$ by K_c and assuming $f_{\text{CdSO}_4} = 1$ in dilute solutions we get,

$$\log K_c - 8A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K - B\mu \quad (8)$$

where, $B = b_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} + b_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ and K is the dissociation constant of CdSO_4 . Plots of $\log K_c - 8A\sqrt{\mu}$ against μ at all the temperatures were linear only upto ca. $\mu = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the intercept of the plots at $\mu = 0$ gave the values of $-\text{p}K$ and the slopes gave the values of B . These values are shown in Table 2. Beyond $\mu = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the points deflect from linearity and the curves bend towards μ axis, showing that other equilibria such as

must be considered.

Heat of dissociation and other thermodynamic quantities: A plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ is found to be linear showing that ΔH^0 is constant. The slope of the plot is $-\Delta H^0/2.3026R$ whence we get values of ΔH^0 . The values of ΔG^0 are obtained from $\text{p}K$ values and the values of ΔS^0 from equation (10),

$$\Delta H^0 = \Delta G^0 + T\Delta S^0 \quad (10)$$

The values are shown in Table 3. So, above ionic strength of ca. 0.02 mol dm^{-3} , considering equation (9) as well, we have

$$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Cd}^{2+}] + [\text{CdSO}_4] + [\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] \quad (11)$$

TABLE 2—VALUES OF pK AND β OF CdSO₄ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	pK		- β (mol ⁻¹ dm ³)	
	Graphical	Statistical	Graphical	Statistical
293.15	2.84	2.84±0.01	27.9	27.9±0.6
298.15	3.00	3.00±0.07	34.5	34.5±4.0
303.15	3.30	3.30±0.00	42.0	42.0±0.0
308.15	3.41	3.41±0.01	52.2	52.2±0.6

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR CdSO₄ (aq) $\rightleftharpoons$ Cd²⁺ (aq) + SO₄²⁻ (aq)

Temp. K	ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\circ$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
293.15	15.9±0.1	64.3±0.5	273.8±1.1
298.15	17.1±0.4	64.3±3.0	273.2±6.4
303.15	19.2±0.0	64.3±0.01	275.4±0.1
308.15	20.1±0.1	64.3±0.4	274.0±0.9

$$\text{and } [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_T = [\text{HSO}_4^-] + [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}} + [\text{CdSO}_4] + 2[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] \quad (12)$$

so,

$$[\text{Cd}^{2+}] = [\text{HSO}_4^-] + [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}} + [\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] - \{[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_T - [\text{Cd}^{2+}]_T\} \quad (13)$$

where $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}}$ is given by equation (6). Now $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]_T = c_2$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_T = c_1 + c_2 + [\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4]$. Putting these values and those of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}$ in equation (13), we get equation (14),

$$[\text{Cd}^{2+}] = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{CaSO}_4} + [\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] \quad (14)$$

The ionic strength of the solution (μ) is given by equation (15),

$$\mu = c_1 + 2c_2 + 2[\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}} - 2[\text{CdSO}_4] \quad (15)$$

In equation (8) values of K and B are known. Putting values of $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}}$ in equation (8) we get

$$\frac{[\text{Cd}^{2+}][\text{CdSO}_4]}{[\text{Cd}^{2+}][\text{CdSO}_4]} = Z \text{ (say)}$$

or $[\text{Cd}^{2+}] = Z [\text{CdSO}_4]$ (16)

Putting equation (16) in equation (11) we get equation (17),

$$c_2 = (Z+1) [\text{CdSO}_4] + [\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] \quad (17)$$

Similarly rewriting equation (12) we get,

$$c_1 + c_2 + [\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4] - [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{free}} = [\text{CdSO}_4] + 2[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] \quad (12a)$$

Solving equations (17) and (12a) we get the values of both $[\text{CdSO}_4]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$. Substituting these values in equation (15) we obtain a new value for μ . The entire process of calculation described above is now repeated till the values of concentrations of different ionic species and of μ become constant upto 10 micro-mol dm⁻³.

The thermodynamic association constant K_1 (reciprocal of dissociation constant) of $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ is given by equation (18),

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]}{[\text{CdSO}_4][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}}}{f_{\text{CdSO}_4} \cdot f_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}} \quad (18)$$

If we represent $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]/[\text{CdSO}_4][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ by $K_{1(A)}$ and consider $f_{\text{CdSO}_4} = 1$,

then

$$\log K_{1(A)} = \log K_1 - \beta_1 \mu \quad (19)$$

where, $\beta_1 = b_{\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}} - b_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$. Plots of $\log K_{1(A)}$ against μ were found to be linear at all temperatures. The intercept of the plots at $\mu = 0$ gave values of $\log K_1$ and the slopes gave values of β_1 . As we could get only 3 to 4 points we did not calculate the values of K_1 or β_1 statistically.

Heat of dissociation and other thermodynamic quantities: Plot of $\log K_1$ against $1/T$ is found to be linear. Hence ΔH_1° is constant. Values of ΔH_1° , ΔG_1° and ΔS_1° have been determined as discussed above for CdSO₄. These values together with the values of $\log K_1$ and β_1 are recorded in Table 4. It will be seen from Table 2 that the

TABLE 4—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR CdSO₄ (aq) + SO₄²⁻ (aq) $\rightleftharpoons$ Cd(SO₄)₂²⁻ (aq)

Temp. K	$\log K_1$	β_1 mol ⁻¹ dm ³	$-\Delta G_1^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_1° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_1° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
293.15	0.18	-61.33	1.01	53.60	186.3
298.15	0.29	-57.77	1.66	53.60	185.3
303.15	0.48	-48.00	2.79	53.60	186.0
308.15	0.66	-41.33	3.89	53.60	186.6

values of K found by us at 298.15 and 308.15 K are of the same order as found by Davies at 298.15 K and Jena and Prasad at 308.15 K but the actual values differ substantially. This is not surprising because we have made several improvements in our measurements.

It will be seen that values of pK and ΔG° are positive over the entire temperature range and the values increase slowly with increase in temperature. These values are slightly greater than the corresponding values for CuSO₄^{1,2} and MnSO₄^{1,2} and behave similarly. This means that the reaction, $\text{CdSO}_4(\text{aq}) \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+}(\text{aq}) + \text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$ or more correctly, $\text{Cd}^{2+}\text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq}) \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+}(\text{aq}) + \text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$ proceeds substantially to the left-hand-side to form ion-pairs, with rise in temperature the equilibrium shifting more towards the left. This is consistent with Bjerrum's theory of ion-pair formation^{14,15}. With rise in temperature the product of dielectric constant of the medium and temperature decreases causing the formation of ion-pairs readily.

It is seen from Table 4 that with rise in temperature the values of $\log K_1$ increase and values of ΔG_1° decrease more and more. This means that with rise in temperature more of $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ is formed. We see that the value of K_1 as determined by us at 308.15 K and that reported by Jena and Prasad is of the same order but differ substantially in magnitude. So far as ΔH° and ΔH_1° values are concerned, the former is negative and the latter positive, but both are constant over the temperature range studied. In the former case it is $-64.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and in the latter case $+53.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. These values are consistent since ΔH° values are measure of energy in breaking and making bonds.

The values of ΔS° for the reaction, $\text{CdSO}_4(\text{aq}) \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+}(\text{aq}) + \text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$ are negative and almost constant over the temperature range. This implies that with dissociation the system becomes more ordered, indicating that $\text{Cd}^{2+}(\text{aq})$ and $\text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$ taken together are more hydrated than the ion-pair $\text{Cd}^{2+}\text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$. This is consistent with the model proposed by Frank and others¹⁶⁻¹⁸ that in aqueous solution the smaller the ions and greater the charge on it the greater is the structure making by these ions. For the reaction, $\text{CdSO}_4(\text{aq}) + \text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq}) \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}(\text{aq})$, the ΔS_1° values are positive and almost constant over the temperature range showing that $\text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$ and $\text{Cd}^{2+}\text{SO}_4^{2-}(\text{aq})$ are more hydrated when taken together than $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}(\text{aq})$.

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